

OSNR-based Hardware Optimization of a Filterless Point-to-Multipoint Network Using Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing

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Abstract—This study investigates the feasibility of deploying digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) in the metro aggregation layer of optical networks. It leverages a real-world network topology provided by Telecom Italia Mobile (TIM), along with its associated traffic patterns, to analyze optical performance, e.g., in terms of optical signal-to-noise-ratio (OSNR). The analysis results are then used to optimize the selection and quantity of optical pluggable transceivers, as well as the placement and number of optical amplifiers required within the network to meet operator-defined performance requirements. Finally, a hardware cost analysis is presented, highlighting the significant cost savings achievable through sublink aggregation in DSCM-enabled point-to-multipoint (P2MP) networks.

Index Terms—Point-to-multipoint optical network, digital subcarrier multiplexing, filterless optical networks, coherent technology, optical aggregation

I. INTRODUCTION

With increasing demands for data rates and flexibility in evolving metro-access networks, managing capital and operational expenses remains crucial [1], [2]. Upgrading these networks based solely on the roadmap defined for core networks is clearly suboptimal.

One key aspect in which they are different is the type of underlying traffic patterns that can be observed: while core networks connect remote sites directly to each other, chiefly via Point-to-Point (P2P) links [3]; the metro-access domain features certain nodes that funnel traffic originating from several endpoints to a higher layer of the optical network (i.e., traffic aggregation). Traditionally, the design and implementation of such regions of an operator's network has involved Intensity Modulation Direct-Detection (IM-DD) transceivers [4], [5], which, despite easily addressing the hardware cost aspect, have to rely on operational techniques to provide connectivity to the complete network (e.g., multiple P2P connections or Time Division Multiplexing (TDM) [5], [6]).

Coherent pluggables, using Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM) with low-speed Digital Subcarriers (DSCs), represents an attractive solution to this situation, since it can both

improve spectral efficiency, thanks to the coherent transmission scheme, and improve the flexibility of the transmission system by allowing the transceivers to dynamically allocate bandwidth resources where needed [7].

Furthermore, this new-found flexibility can be used to reduce costs by decreasing the number of required pluggable transceivers and Operational Expenditures (OPEXs) across the optical network [8]. Previously, we have carried out both performance and cost-based analysis on networks provided by Telecom Italia Mobile (TIM) depending on the direction of the traffic flow [9]. To expand on these analyses, we now investigate the optimization of similar network topologies in terms of hardware components constrained by potential performance requirements (i.e., Optical Signal-to-Noise-Ratio (OSNR) margin defined by operators as minimum acceptable operating conditions).

In this paper, Sec. II describes the general concept of the tool used in the numerical analysis together with the methodology. In addition, we present TIM's network topology and the most relevant characteristics for the simulations. Sec. III discusses the results of the network-level optimization. The conclusions of our analysis are summarized in Sec. IV.

II. SIMULATION CONDITIONS

A. General concept

The numerical analysis of the network topology stems from the concept presented in [9]: the evaluation of a DSCM-powered Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) network is carried out based on its operating conditions. More specifically, the analysis mainly focuses on the OSNR margin and level of sublink aggregation (i.e., the degree of resource sharing at the hub nodes). To determine the OSNR margin, it is necessary to calculate the OSNR evolution across the network as the DSCM signals propagate by considering power losses (i.e., fiber attenuation, coupling losses, connector losses, etc.) and noise originating from the Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifiers (EDFAs).

Furthermore, by also incorporating potential nonlinear transmission penalties of the pluggable transceivers, compared to the back-to-back scenario, it is possible to provide a more realistic view of the performance of the optical system. Whereas the OSNR margin relates specifically to the

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physical-layer behavior of the optical signals, the level of aggregation (T_{AGG} as defined in [9]) refers to one of the main advantages of P2MP DSCM technologies: condensing and centralizing communication capabilities at a hub node – how many optical sublinks can be served by a single Tx/Rx source at the hub [9]. The said transceiver is then capable of directly establishing connections to several endpoints across multiple optical branches simultaneously, provided that the network follows a filterless node architecture [9], [10]. In this regard, a single high-speed 400G P2MP transceiver, which generates a DSCM 16×25 Gbit/s optical signal using 16 Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (16-QAM) and dual polarization, could potentially be used to communicate with up to 16 leaf nodes. In a metro-access scenario, where networks are structured according to a hub-and-spoke architecture and leaf nodes are placed in horseshoe-shaped connections (i.e., branches or sublinks) which connect hub nodes to provide a main and a protection path for traffic, these high-speed pluggables at the hub nodes could be used to serve all or a particular set of these sublinks. The degree to which the resource sharing can be implemented is a function of the traffic requirements of the leaf nodes that need to be served, as well as by OSNR margin of the individual connections.

B. Network topology

The analysis presented in this paper is based on the network topology depicted in Fig. 1, which consists of four sublinks or horseshoes. At the ends of the horseshoe links, there are two hub nodes (\boxed{A} and \boxed{B}), where one represents the main connection and the second, the protection path. The networks are designed so that the leaf nodes in the optical links can communicate with both hub nodes, where possible. In this particular scenario, this is not possible for the 10.5 km-long optical link (sublink 4), since it only connects to hub \boxed{A} . This has the implication that the high-speed DSCM pluggables at the hub nodes cannot aggregate sublinks in the same way. While a single transceiver at hub \boxed{A} is capable of achieving full aggregation by distributing the optical signal simultaneously among all four sublinks, hub \boxed{B} can only communicate with up to three sublinks in parallel, because there is no connection to the leaf node at the end of sublink 4. The degree to which a single source connects to one or multiple sublinks is called ‘the level of aggregation’ and has been defined in [9] as follows:

$$T_{AGG} = \frac{1}{M} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^M L_{AGG_i}, \quad (1)$$

where M refers to the total number of combined horseshoes that are needed to guarantee that the entire topology is connected, and L_{AGG_i} denotes the number of sublinks that are being aggregated. For example, when considering that traffic flows in the direction towards hub \boxed{B} , full aggregation is possible by using a single source ($M = 1$) at the hub to provide connectivity to all four sublinks at once; this corresponds to a T_{AGG} of 4. On the other hand, in the opposite direction

(i.e., when traffic is directed towards hub \boxed{A}), due to the asymmetry in the network topology, two sources ($M = 2$) are required for the maximum aggregation level possible: one transceiver communicates with the nodes in sublinks 1–3, and a second transceiver is required exclusively for sublink 4. Therefore, this latter scenario exhibits a T_{AGG} equal to 2.

Fig. 1: Example of a network from TIM. Different types of nodes are represented by the following symbols: hub nodes (\square), leaf nodes (\circ), and transit nodes (\diamond).

The network topology in Fig. 1 illustrates hub (\square), leaf (\circ) and transit nodes (\diamond). The hub nodes symbolize the traffic aggregator locations towards the backbone of an operator’s optical network. Typically, these sites will house IP routers capable of supporting high-speed transmission up to 400GbE per interface port. In a similar way, leaf nodes also act as traffic aggregator nodes, but rather towards the endpoints/users of the network, defining the overall data rate requirements of the different sublinks that the high-speed pluggable transceivers at the hub nodes must be capable of addressing. Transit nodes are operator sites that have not yet been prepared with the necessary infrastructure (e.g., amplifiers, cooling systems, racks, electrical power, optical components, etc.) to house equipment, but which could at any point in the future be set up accordingly should the need arise. For this reason, while traffic is not added to the network at these nodes, in our analysis, they symbolize physical positions along a particular optical path where EDFAs could be placed if needed/desired.

Horseshoe ID	Traffic requirements	Total distance
Sublink 1	5.4 [Gb/s]	31.9 [km]
Sublink 2	13.2 [Gb/s]	54.1 [km]
Sublink 3	110.9 [Gb/s]	66.1 [km]
Sublink 4	6.5 [Gb/s]	10.5 [km]
Total traffic	136.0 [Gb/s]	

TABLE I: Traffic requirements and total distance for the sublinks in TIM’s network topology illustrated in Fig. 1.

Table I summarizes the data rate requirements of the different sublinks in the network, where the identifiers for the horseshoes/sublinks are labeled from top to bottom according to the topology in Fig. 1.

Fig. 2: Numerical simulations for OSNR margins as a function of the number of additional EDFAs required (i.e., amplifiers located at transit nodes) according to various possible aggregation levels, the data rate requirements in I, and the conditions regarding the direction of the traffic flow.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

A. Performance analysis and methodology

After calculating the OSNR of the network for a particular scenario, we compare this value to the threshold where the coherent P2MP pluggables' performance is still capable of delivering error-free data transmission after decoding. This difference is what we refer to as the 'OSNR margin'. The results shown in Fig. 2 use this metric to express the quality of transmission given the number of amplifiers in the network for three general scenarios: traffic flowing towards hub \boxed{B} (no protection path), traffic flowing towards hub \boxed{A} (no protection path), and traffic flowing in both directions over different fibers.

When observing the results depicted in Fig. 2, it must be noted that the placement of EDFAs in TIM's network topology is a combinatorial problem, as there are multiple places where an amplifier can be activated. Consequently, each of these combinations (i.e., scenarios) will exhibit its own value for the network's OSNR margin, since nonlinear penalties and OSNR levels of the signals will be different depending on if and where the extra amplifiers are introduced.

To exemplify the impact of these amplifiers at transit nodes, Fig. 3 depicts a subset of possible combinations for a network with three additional EDFAs. In this illustration, the traffic flow is to be assumed to correspond to the \boxed{A} -to- \boxed{B} direction and a $T_{AGG} = 4$ (i.e., all sublinks connected to the same high-speed pluggable transceiver at the hub). For reference, without any additional amplifiers at the transit nodes, the network exhibits an OSNR margin of -2.26 dB; meaning that the network does not perform well enough to guarantee error-free operation of the transceivers. In Fig. 3 (a), we have placed three additional amplifiers in the bottom two sublinks, slightly improving the network's OSNR margin level to -1.31 dB, which is still below the operational threshold of the pluggables. By testing different combinations, we discovered that placing an amplifier at the coupling stage that combines the top two sublinks leads to a noticeable performance

Fig. 3: Visual representation of a subset of scenarios with three amplifiers that are located at transit nodes. The locations of the amplifiers are indicated by the yellow (light)-colored hexagons (\circ).

improvement. Fig. 3(b) corresponds to an improved scenario with an OSNR margin of 1.48 dB, which already would allow the coherent P2MP transceivers to operate according to specifications. However, the placement of the other two EDFAs in this scenario is not optimal, being right after leaf nodes; potentially, introducing a slight penalty due to high power levels. Finally, Fig. 3 (c) illustrates the placement of the amplifiers that yields the highest OSNR margin: 2.55 dB. In total, a network scenario with three possible additional EDFAs at transit nodes has 84 different possible combinations to place the amplifiers (see Table II). Among all of these, Fig. 3 (c) is the best-performing one; this is the type of data that is reflected in Fig. 2: best-performing configurations of the EDFAs for particular hardware conditions (i.e., sublink aggregation).

gation configuration). In Table II, please note that the values in the 'EDFAs' column correspond to the effective number of transit nodes where additional amplifiers can be placed; these can depend on the topology and aggregation conditions of the network. For instance, if sublink 1 and sublink 2 are not aggregated (e.g., $T_{AGG} = 1$), their optical signals will be treated as parallel optical connections. Therefore, at the transit nodes closest to hub node B , each of them would have to have their own set of EDFAs to amplify the signals. For this reason, the number of amplifiers at transit nodes in Table II goes up to 11. On the other hand, if sublink 1 and sublink 2 are assumed to connect to the same transceiver at the hub node, the signals will be combined at a coupling stage. In this scenario, at the transit nodes closest to hub node B , single EDFA units are capable of amplifying the resulting combined signal. Consequently, there are only 9 possible transit node locations where amplifiers can be introduced. In Table II, the values corresponding to network scenarios where sublink 1 and sublink 2 are combined are expressed in parentheses.

EDFAs	Combinations	EDFAs	Combinations
0	1 / (1)	6	462 / (84)
1	11 / (9)	7	330 / (36)
2	55 / (36)	8	165 / (9)
3	165 / (84)	9	55 / (1)
4	330 / (126)	10	11 / (-)
5	462 / (126)	11	1 / (-)

TABLE II: Possible number of placement combinations according to the number of amplifiers at the transit nodes assuming traffic flows in an A -to- B direction. Values in parentheses correspond to scenarios where the optical signals of sublink 1 and sublink 2 are combined, reducing the number of effective transit nodes.

Due to all possible combination scenarios and due to focusing on the best-performing hardware configuration, the graphs showing the performance analysis do not necessarily exhibit a noticeable OSNR worsening when the number of EDFAs increases; depending on the aggregation conditions, there might be transit nodes (\odot) where amplifiers can be placed and not affect the limiting conditions of the network, since the overall OSNR margin could be determined by a different sublink. By comparing the results in Fig. 2 (a) and (b), we confirm that the network is not symmetric, and it is therefore not possible for both scenarios to exactly enable the same levels of aggregation. Furthermore, since the node and element placement along the sublinks is not the same, the performance is different depending on the traffic flow direction. Another important aspect to consider when both traffic flow directions are assumed as independent events (i.e., no protection path) is that the plotted data points for a given number of EDFAs do not necessarily mean that this performance level is achieved with amplifier(s) at the same transit node(s). From a cost perspective in real-life provisioning, it would be useful for an operator to identify in advance the critical node(s) where the infrastructure to support additional equipment (e.g., am-

plifiers) will have to be prepared, so as to ensure an adequate performance level for both the main and protection paths. For this reason, we investigated a combined scenario (Fig. 2 (c)), where the depicted best-case OSNR margin corresponds to the worse value between both traffic flow directions under the constraint that the EDFA placement conditions match. In contrast, however, levels of aggregation do not necessarily have to match. Consequently, we defined a combined level of aggregation (C_{AGG}) as the average of both traffic flow directions:

$$C_{AGG} = \frac{T_{AGG-AtoB} + T_{AGG-BtoA}}{2} \quad (2)$$

Incidentally, defining C_{AGG} is also a combinatorial problem, since the level of aggregation corresponding to the main traffic flow direction does not necessarily have to match the level of aggregation of the protection path; hence the increase in the total number of aggregation levels in Fig. 2 (c). Nevertheless, despite the differences in terms of approach, the graph in Fig. 2 (c) reads and exhibits the same logic as Fig. 2 (a-b).

B. Hardware-based cost analysis

Fig. 4: Number of additional amplifiers in the topology required to achieve a given OSNR margin threshold.

When planning a network, operators will express multiple conditions/requirements that the network proposals from equipment manufacturers should fulfill. One of these parameters is a desired OSNR margin value. While it is not possible to define a single value, since it depends on very specific circumstances such as the network topology, the particular requirements of a telecom operator, the technology being deployed, we can generalize and express our results in relation to possible desired OSNR values. By reorganizing Fig. 2 (c), it is possible to obtain a clearer view of the hardware needed to guarantee certain operating conditions in the network. In this regard, Fig. 4 depicts the number of EDFAs that have to be additionally activated at the transit nodes as a function of

the desired OSNR margin. In this depiction, we can observe how and when certain provisioning conditions (i.e., levels of aggregation at the hub nodes) require extra hardware to ensure that given operating thresholds are met.

Knowing the hardware conditions of the network required to realize a given scenario, we could express them as deployment costs (i.e., Capital Expenditure (CAPEX)). To calculate this value we have defined a cost structure based on Arbitrary Cost Units (acu). According to the sublinks' traffic characteristics in Table I, we have selected coherent transceivers of different data rates, which are capable of addressing those demands by supporting DSCM capabilities, and price tags. In a way similar to our previous work in [9], Table III summarizes the hardware and the corresponding cost per unit.

Hardware element	Cost
100G coherent pluggable	2.7 [acu]
200G coherent pluggable	3 [acu]
400G coherent pluggable	4 [acu]
EDFA	4 [acu]

TABLE III: Cost values in terms of [acu] for the hardware elements being optimized.

From the values in the Table III, we can conclude that the linear increase in data rate as traffic increases is better addressed by acquiring higher-speed transceivers rather than by using multiple lower-speed ones. In the case of P2MP DSCM, this is particularly useful at the hub nodes, since we are then able to upgrade from bookended connections requiring multiple low-speed transceivers to fewer high-speed transceivers, which are able to communicate with multiple leaf nodes in parallel. However, this is possible only as long as the technical requirements related to traffic requirements can be addressed (i.e., having sufficient Subcarriers (SCs) available at the hub node's transceiver to enable the required connections to the leaf nodes). In regards to EDFAs, the unit cost is as high as a 400G transceiver, since we have to account for chassis, power supply, and management functionalities, among others.

The results showing the cost of implementing a network that ensures a minimum OSNR margin level are displayed in Fig. 5 for the scenario that considers both traffic directions as a function of the possible combined aggregation levels. To put the cost of provisioning the network for P2MP operation into context, a dashed line depicting the cost of deploying an approach based on P2P transceivers and connections has been added to the graph. For this threshold line, we assume that the cost of the pluggable transceivers required to address the traffic conditions at the leaf nodes will be replicated at both the main hub node and the protection hub. Due to the complexity required for a more thorough analysis with respect to any potential required amplifiers, we have decided to ignore any possible need of EDFAs to ensure a particular OSNR margin level for the P2P scenario.

The first aspect to notice in Fig. 5 is that, in general, by reducing the number of pluggable transceivers required to ensure connectivity across a complete network, a P2MP-oriented provisioning approach would result in lower implementation

Fig. 5: Deployment cost of the scenarios depicted in Fig. 2 (c) that are capable of providing an OSNR margin performance capable of addressing the desired levels. The dashed line represents the cost for a P2P-oriented provisioning of the network.

costs compared to a more traditional P2P communication paradigm according to the cost scheme in Table III. Then, the analysis data indicate that, depending on the OSNR margin desired by the operator for their networks, there might be hardware configurations that are more appropriate than others in terms of reducing the overall hardware acquisition cost. For example, $C_{AGG} = 1.66$ corresponds to the lowest cost as long as the desired margin is between 0 and 1 dB; for moderately higher margin values (e.g., 2 – 4 dB), $C_{AGG} = 1.5$ offers the best cost alternative; and for OSNR margins beyond 5 dB, combined aggregation levels $C_{AGG} \leq 1.33$ are required. This behavior reveals broad implications for aggregation levels and OSNR margin requirements: increasing the level of aggregation helps to lower the implementation cost, since the number of transceiver units at the hub sites is reduced by means of single sources serving multiple sublinks simultaneously. This statement, however, leads to question the combined aggregation levels $C_{AGG} > 1.66$, since they do not lower the cost value: for a minimum margin of 0 dB, no hardware combination is able to be as cost-efficient as $C_{AGG} = 1.66$. The reason for this can be inferred from Fig. 2 (c): all of the implementations with larger combined aggregation levels require at least one EDFA (per traffic flow direction) to achieve an OSNR margin value ≥ 0 dB. Besides the deployment cost of the additional amplifiers needed, another challenge of high aggregation levels (which can also be observed in Fig. 2 (c)) is the fact that the OSNR budget for the optical system is not only heavily affected by the coupler losses and the optical noise in the network, but also by the intra-signal power imbalance seen by the pluggable at the hub. For instance, let us assume that no additional amplifiers are required at full aggregation; here, at hub **A** ($T_{AGG} = 4$), the high-speed pluggable will likely detect a strong difference in power between the SCs originating at sublink 1 and sublink 4 due to the different link

characteristics (e.g., distance, number of nodes and amplifiers, types of fiber, etc.). On the other hand, by not combining sublinks (i.e., by reducing the aggregation level) it is possible to achieve higher OSNR margin levels at the expense of a higher deployment cost. It is important, however, to remember that Fig. 2 (c) and, consequently, Fig. 5 depict the margin data and cost of the best performing hardware conditions. If, by contrast, the optimization criterion was the lowest possible deployment cost, the results would correspond to the most resource-efficient implementations; probably sacrificing range in terms of the OSNR margin that can be effectively achieved.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have investigated the relation between sublink aggregation and deployment cost in coherent P2MP DSCM metro-access networks. Our analysis focuses on the performance optimization of a realistic topology by selecting the combination of high-speed transceivers at the hub nodes and the placement of EDFAs across the network that maximize the OSNR margin of the optical system. By performing the role of an operator in defining a desired margin level and based on a comprehensive cost breakdown of the different hardware elements (e.g., coherent pluggable transceivers and optical amplifiers), we demonstrate the effectiveness of sublink aggregation in the metro aggregation domain to reduce cost for an eventual deployment of a network.

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